

The Impact of Long Vacation Logbook and Report Presentation on the Clinical Competence of Student Radiographers in the University of Maiduguri

^{*1}Abubakar G. Mathew, ²Excel Ademola Shola, ³Esther A. Zamdai, ⁴Nurudeen M. Gunda, ⁵Nkubli B. Flavious, ⁶Alhamdu Silas Moi

*Corresponding author: mattosky@unimaid.edu.ng

^{1,2,3,4,5,6} Department of Medical Radiography, College of Medical Sciences, Faculty of Allied Health Sciences, University of Maiduguri, Borno state.

Abstract

This study examined the impact of long vacation logbook documentation and report presentation on the clinical competence of student radiographers at the University of Maiduguri, Nigeria. A descriptive survey design was adopted, involving 150 radiography students that were selected purposively from 300 to 500 level students at their clinical level. Data were collected using a structured questionnaire which underwent content validity by the professional in the department, and analysed using descriptive statistics, including frequency count, percentage, and mean score. The findings revealed that most respondents had attended more than one long vacation clinical posting, with 38% attending two postings and 30% attending three postings. In terms of attendance frequency, 63.1% of the students reported always attending long vacation postings, while 28.2% attended sometimes. Hands-on clinical experience was identified as the primary motivation for participation, accounting for 76.7% of the responses. However, only 41.3% of the students reported keeping a logbook during long vacation postings, while 58.7% did not document their clinical experiences. Further findings indicate that long vacation clinical postings had an impact on respondents' understanding of clinical procedures, enhanced accountability, promoted reflective learning, and increased their confidence in performing clinical tasks. The cumulative mean score of 4.07 indicated a strong positive impact of the clinical posting activities on clinical competence. The study concludes that long vacation clinical postings provide valuable opportunities for practical learning among radiography students. It recommends the enforcement of mandatory logbook documentation and structured report presentations to strengthen reflective learning and improve clinical competence.

Keywords: Logbook, Report Presentation, Clinical Competence, Student Radiographers, Long Vacation Postings

Introduction

Radiography education in Nigeria combines theoretical classroom instruction with clinical training in hospital environments (Ogbu, 2008; Ohagwu, et al., 2016). The training process enables students to progress from novice learners to competent radiographers capable of delivering quality diagnostic imaging services and patient care. Clinical training is therefore essential for the acquisition of practical skills, professional attitudes, and competencies required for radiography

practice (Akpaniwo et al., 2018). Through structured clinical exposure, students develop technical competence in imaging procedures, patient positioning, radiation safety, and equipment operation. Such training ensures that radiography graduates possess the necessary professional skills to function effectively in healthcare settings (Shafuda et al., 2024).

Clinical training for radiography students at the University of Maiduguri begins at the third year of study, during which students are posted to the University of Maiduguri Teaching Hospital several times weekly during academic sessions. In addition to these routine clinical postings, students are required to participate in long vacation clinical postings during academic breaks. These postings provide extended opportunities for hands-on clinical experience because students have greater access to diagnostic equipment and exposure to diverse imaging procedures compared to the limited time available during semester postings. Consequently, long vacation clinical postings have been identified as an important component of radiography education that supports the development of clinical competence among students (Ohagwu et al., 2016).

Empirical evidence suggests that clinical exposure during long vacation postings is highly beneficial to radiography students. A study conducted among undergraduate radiography students in northwestern Nigeria reported that approximately 68% of students considered long vacation clinical posting to be highly educative despite the challenges associated with it (Akpaniwo et al., 2018). This finding highlights the importance of extended clinical exposure in strengthening students' practical skills and reinforcing theoretical knowledge acquired in the classroom.

Problem-based learning approaches also emphasize the role of real-world experiences in developing critical thinking and clinical competence among healthcare students. In this context, students are exposed to real-life clinical situations that require them to apply theoretical knowledge in solving practical problems (Hmelo-Silver, 2004). Long vacation clinical postings therefore provide valuable opportunities for radiography students to engage in problem-based learning through direct interaction with clinical cases, imaging equipment, and healthcare professionals. To maximize the benefits of experiential clinical training, educational tools such as logbooks and report presentations are often used to document and evaluate students' clinical experiences. Logbooks serve as structured records of clinical activities, procedures performed, and cases encountered by students during training. They also enable educators to monitor students' clinical exposure and ensure that learning objectives are achieved. Report presentations, on the other hand, encourage students to reflect on their clinical experiences and communicate their observations and findings in a systematic manner. These tools are widely recognized as effective strategies for promoting reflective learning, critical thinking, and professional development among healthcare students (Kilminster et al., 2007).

Feedback is another important component of clinical education because it allows students to evaluate their performance and identify areas for improvement. Through feedback obtained from supervisors and instructors, students are able to refine their clinical skills, correct errors, and improve their overall performance (Mifflin et al., 2017). Logbooks and report presentations can therefore serve as platforms through which meaningful feedback is provided to students during clinical training.

The relationship between logbooks, report presentations, and adherence to clinical postings is also significant in educational settings. When these activities are mandatory, students are more likely to participate actively in clinical postings because they are required to document their experiences and present them for evaluation. However, when logbooks and report presentations are not strictly enforced, students may perceive clinical postings as less important, resulting in reduced participation and accountability (Kilminster et al., 2007). This situation may negatively affect the overall effectiveness of clinical training.

Clinical competence refers to the ability of healthcare professionals to effectively integrate knowledge, skills, and professional attitudes in delivering patient care. In radiography practice, clinical competence involves the accurate performance of imaging procedures, adherence to safety standards, and effective communication with patients and other healthcare professionals. Structured assessment tools such as logbooks and reflective reports have been shown to improve clinical competence by encouraging continuous practice, reflection, and feedback during training (Epstein & Hundert, 2002).

In recent years, however, there has been a noticeable decline in adherence to long vacation clinical postings among radiography students at the University of Maiduguri. Unlike intra-semester clinical postings that are supervised within the teaching hospital environment, long vacation postings are often voluntary and lack strict monitoring mechanisms. As a result, some students do not fully participate in these postings or fail to document their clinical experiences adequately. The absence of structured requirements such as mandatory logbooks and report presentations may contribute to reduced participation and accountability among students. Although logbooks and report presentations are recognized as effective tools for enhancing clinical education, their impact on clinical competence may vary depending on the level of student participation and institutional implementation. Therefore, there is a need to evaluate how the use of long vacation logbooks and report presentations influences adherence to clinical postings and the development of clinical competence among radiography students.

This study therefore examines the impact of long vacation logbook documentation and report presentation on the clinical competence of student radiographers at the University of Maiduguri. The findings are expected to provide insights that may contribute to improving clinical training practices and strengthening radiography education in Nigeria

Objectives of the Study

The main objective of this study was to examine the impact of long vacation logbook documentation and report presentation on the clinical competence of student radiographers at the University of Maiduguri.

The specific objectives were to:

1. Identify Student Radiographers' Participation in Long Vacation Clinical Postings.
2. examine the frequency of Long Vacation Posting Attendance among student Radiographers

3. Identify Student Radiographers' Motivations for Participation in Long Vacation Clinical Postings
4. examine Usage and frequency of use of Logbook during Long Vacation Clinical Postings among Radiography Students
5. Determine the perceived impact of long vacation logbook documentation and report presentation on the clinical competence of student radiographers.

Theoretical Review

This study is anchored on experiential learning theory, which emphasizes learning through experience and reflection. Experiential learning theory explains that knowledge is created through the transformation of experience into meaningful understanding (Kolb, 1984). The theory suggests that effective learning occurs when learners engage actively in experiences and subsequently reflect on those experiences to develop new knowledge and skills.

Experiential learning occurs through a four-stage cycle consisting of concrete experience, reflective observation, abstract conceptualization, and active experimentation. In clinical education, concrete experience occurs when students participate in practical clinical activities such as imaging procedures and patient care. These experiences form the foundation upon which further learning is built. Reflective observation involves examining and reflecting on these experiences in order to understand what occurred and why it happened. Logbooks play an important role at this stage because they provide students with a structured means of documenting their clinical activities and reflecting on their performance. Through documentation, students are able to analyze their strengths and weaknesses and identify areas that require improvement.

Abstract conceptualization involves connecting clinical experiences with theoretical knowledge. Report presentations facilitate this stage by encouraging students to analyze their observations and relate them to theoretical principles learned in the classroom. This process strengthens students' conceptual understanding of radiographic procedures and clinical decision-making.

The final stage, active experimentation, occurs when students apply newly acquired knowledge and insights in future clinical situations. By practicing improved techniques and applying lessons learned from reflection, students enhance their clinical competence and professional confidence. Experiential learning theory therefore supports the integration of logbooks and report presentations in clinical education because these tools facilitate reflection, knowledge integration, and continuous improvement in clinical practice.

Literature Review

Several studies have examined the role of logbooks and reflective documentation in enhancing clinical competence among healthcare students (Kumsa et al., 2022; Coleman et al., 2024). Research conducted among radiography students found that structured clinical documentation significantly enhanced students' learning experiences and improved their ability to apply theoretical knowledge in practical imaging procedures (O'Connor et al., 2024). Students reported

that maintaining logbooks helped them track clinical experiences and increased their confidence in performing diagnostic imaging tasks.

Similarly, Sandy et al., (2021) investigated the use of reflective writing among paramedic students and found that structured documentation significantly improved students' decision-making abilities and integration of theoretical knowledge with practical clinical scenarios. Students who engaged in reflective documentation demonstrated higher confidence in performing clinical tasks compared to those who did not.

Evidence from medical training programmes also indicates that logbooks are valuable assessment tools for monitoring students' clinical experiences and competencies (Awang Besar et al., 2025; Mokhtar et al., 2024). A study conducted in Kenya revealed that the use of logbooks for workplace-based assessments improved the accuracy of clinical documentation and enhanced students' procedural skills (Kipkulei et al., 2022). When combined with structured clinical examinations, logbooks were found to contribute significantly to improved clinical performance.

In resource-constrained environments similar to Nigeria, logbooks have also been identified as effective tools for tracking clinical progress and enhancing procedural competence. Studies conducted among radiography students in Ethiopia reported that structured logbook documentation improved students' confidence and competence in performing imaging procedures ((Kumsa et al., 2022). However, limited supervision during clinical placements was identified as a challenge that affected the effectiveness of logbook usage.

Within the Nigerian context, research has also highlighted the importance of structured clinical documentation in radiography training (Chia et al., 2024; Elechi et al., 2025). Maduka, et al. (2021) conducted a survey among radiography educators, the study revealed strong support for the use of logbooks in clinical training programmes, with most respondents indicating that structured logbook assessments contribute significantly to the development of competent radiographers. Similarly, studies among radiology residents in Nigeria found that maintaining clinical logbooks improved procedural competence and helped organize clinical experiences for examination preparation (Idowu, 2018).

Despite these benefits, some studies have reported limited utilization of logbooks due to factors such as inadequate supervision, lack of awareness, and institutional constraints (Upadhayay & Guragain2022; Awang Besar et al., 2025). For instance, research among practicing radiographers revealed that only a small proportion regularly used logbooks for documenting clinical experiences, although those who did reported improvements in diagnostic accuracy and professional competence (Ugwu, et al.,2009).

Furthermore, Abdullah Omar et al. (2021) conducted a mixed-methods study among undergraduate medical students and found that logbooks significantly improved students' engagement and understanding during clinical rotations. The study reported that over 75% of students considered logbooks useful for learning, while teachers noted that the tool enhanced students' accountability and reflective practice. However, the effectiveness of logbooks was influenced by factors such as quality of feedback and supervision.

Existing literature demonstrates that logbooks and reflective documentation contribute significantly to the development of clinical competence in healthcare education (Saba et al., 2024; Awang Besar et al., 2025). However, there is limited empirical evidence regarding the impact of voluntary logbook use during long vacation clinical postings among radiography students in Nigeria. This study therefore seeks to address this gap by examining how logbook documentation and report presentations influence the clinical competence of student radiographers at the University of Maiduguri.

Methodology

This study used a descriptive survey design to examine how extended vacation logbook documentation and report presentation affected student radiographers' clinical competency. The University of Maiduguri radiography students who had taken part in extended vacation clinical placements made up the study population. A structured online survey created with Google Forms was used to gather research data from the students. Demographic information, long-term vacation participation, logbook and report usage, perceived influence on clinical competence, and student recommendations for enhancing clinical training were all covered in the questionnaire. The study's participants were chosen using a purposive sampling technique.

The sample size was determined using Taro Yamane’s formula for sample size determination. Based on an estimated population of 240 radiography students, the calculated sample size was approximately 150 respondents. The inclusion criteria consisted of radiography students in 300, 400, and 500 levels who had participated in clinical postings. Students in 100 and 200 levels, as well as radiography students from other universities, were excluded from the study because they were not at clinical level of their study. The research instrument was validated through expert review to ensure face validity and clarity of the questionnaire items. The survey data were analysed with the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 20. Descriptive statistics such as frequency count and percentage were used to summarise and present the findings. Participation in the study was voluntary, and respondents were assured that their responses would be treated confidentially and used strictly for research purposes.

Results

Demographic Information

Table 1: Demography Profile of students (N=150)

Demographics	Categories	Frequency	Percent
Gender	Male	96	64.0%
	Female	54	36.0%
Level of Study	300 Level	31	20.7%
	400 Level	54	36.0%
	500 Level	65	43.3%
	Total	150	100%

The gender distribution shows that males make up nearly two-thirds of the respondents (64%), while females account for just over a third (36%). This indicates a male-dominated sample, which may reflect gender enrollment patterns in the department. Most respondents are in their final years of study, with 43.3% in 500 level and 36.0% in 400 level. The 300 level students make up about a fifth of the sample. This reflects that long vacation postings are more heavily attended by advanced students who are closer to graduation.

Table 2: Students’ Participation in Long Vacation Posting

Questions	YES	NO
Have you ever participated in long vacation clinical posting?	148 (98.7%)	2 (1.3%)

Virtually all respondents (98.7%) reported participating in at least one long vacation posting. This emphasizes the central role postings play in clinical education. The negligible number who have not participated (2 students).

Attendance to Long Vacation Posting

Table 3: Long Vacation Posting Attended Attendance

Research Question	1	2	3	4
How many long vacation posting have you attended?	19 (12.8%)	56 (38%)	44 (30%)	29 (19.2%)

The table 3 presents the distribution of the number of long vacation clinical postings attended by radiography students at the University of Maiduguri. The results show that the largest proportion of respondents, 56 students (38%), reported attending two long vacation postings. This was followed by 44 students (30%) who indicated that they had attended three postings. Additionally, 29 students (19.2%) reported attending four postings, while a smaller proportion, 19 students (12.8%), indicated that they had attended only one long vacation posting. Overall, the findings suggest that most of the students had participated in more than one long vacation clinical posting, indicating a relatively high level of engagement in extended clinical training. The fact that the majority attended two or three postings demonstrates consistent participation in clinical practice opportunities, which may contribute positively to the development of clinical skills and competence among the students. However, the presence of a smaller group that attended only one posting may indicate variations in participation levels, possibly due to factors such as scheduling conflicts, personal constraints, or limited enforcement of participation requirements, which could hinder their overall clinical experience and skill development compared to their peers.

Frequency of Attendance of Long Vacation Postings

Table 4: frequency of Attendance of Long Vacation Postings

Research Question	Always	Sometimes	Rarely	Never
How often do you attend long vacation postings?	94 (63.1%)	42 (28.2%)	10 (6.7%)	3 (2%)

Above table presents the frequency of attendance of radiography students at long vacation clinical postings. The results indicate that the majority of the respondents, 94 students (63.1%), reported that they always attend long vacation postings. This suggests a high level of participation among the students in clinical training during vacation periods. Additionally, 42 students (28.2%) indicated that they sometimes attend the postings, reflecting a moderate level of participation among a considerable proportion of the respondents.

However, a smaller number of students reported lower levels of attendance. Specifically, 10 students (6.7%) indicated that they rarely attend long vacation postings; only 3 students (2%) reported that they never attend such postings. These findings generally suggest that most radiography students regularly participate in long vacation clinical postings, which may contribute positively to the development of their practical skills and clinical competence.

Table 5: Motivations for Participation in Long Vacation Clinical Postings

S/No	I am Motivated by	frequency	Percent
1	Hands-on clinical experience	115	76.7%
2	Availability of equipment	15	10.0%
3	Freedom from academic workload	10	6.7%
4	Mandatory report/logbook	6	4.0%
5	Peer influence	4	2.7%

The results in table 5 indicate that the primary motivation for participation is the opportunity to gain practical clinical experience, as reported by 115 students (76.7%). This demonstrates that most students recognise the importance of hands-on training in developing the technical skills and competencies necessary for professional radiology practice.

A smaller percentage of participants, 15 students (10.0%), indicated that the availability of equipment motivates their participation in training during extended holidays. This may reflect the opportunity for students to access and operate diagnostic imaging equipment more frequently during holiday periods when clinical facilities are less busy. Additionally, 10 participants (6.7%) reported that freedom from academic workload is a motivating factor, meaning that the absence of regular academic activities during the holiday period allows them to focus more on practical training.

Furthermore, a small number of participants indicated that their participation was motivated by specific academic requirements. Specifically, 6 students (4.0%) reported that writing mandatory reports or documenting records was a motivating factor for their attendance, while 4 students (2.7%) indicated that peer influence encouraged their participation.

Overall, the results suggest that intrinsic professional motivation, particularly the desire to gain practical clinical experience, plays a more significant role in encouraging participation in clinical rotations during extended breaks than external factors such as peer influence or academic requirements.

Table 6: Usage and frequency of use of Logbook during Long Vacation Clinical Postings

Questions	Responses	
	Yes	No
Do you keep a logbook during long vacation posting?	62 (41.3%)	88 (58.7%)
If yes, how often do you fill it in?	Daily	15 (24.2%)
	Weekly	7 (11.3%)
	Occasionally	35 (56.5%)
	At the end of posting	5 (8.0%)

Regarding the first question (table 6) on whether students keep a logbook during their long vacation postings, the results show that 62 respondents (41.3%) indicated that they maintain a logbook, while a larger proportion, 88 respondents (58.7%), reported that they do not keep a logbook. This finding suggests that the majority of the students do not document their clinical activities through logbooks during the long vacation period, which may limit structured monitoring and reflection on their clinical experiences.

For those who reported keeping a logbook, the second question examined how frequently they completed their entries. The results indicate that the majority of these students, 35 respondents (56.5%), filled in their logbooks occasionally. Additionally, 15 students (24.2%) reported that they documented their activities daily, while 7 respondents (11.3%) indicated that they completed their logbooks weekly. A smaller proportion, 5 respondents (8.0%), reported that they filled in their logbooks only at the end of the posting.

These findings suggest that although a portion of the students utilise logbooks during long vacation clinical postings, consistent documentation practices remain limited. Most students who maintain logbooks do not complete them regularly, which may reduce the effectiveness of logbooks as tools for tracking clinical activities, promoting reflective learning, and enhancing the development of clinical competence among student radiographers.

Perceived Impact of Long Vacation Logbook Documentation and Report Presentation on the Clinical Competence of Student Radiographers.

Table 7: Impact of Long Vacation Logbook Documentation and Report Presentation on the Clinical Competence

Table with 6 columns: Statement, SA, A, D, SD, Mean. Rows include statements like 'Keeping a logbook improved competence' and 'Report presentations improved understanding'.

Table 7 presents the perceived impact of long vacation logbook documentation and report presentations on the clinical competence of student radiographers. The results show that majority of the respondents strongly agreed or agreed with most of the statements, indicating positive perceptions of the role of logbooks and report presentations in improving clinical competence.

Specifically, 72 respondents (48.0%) strongly agreed and 54 (36.0%) agreed that keeping a logbook improved their clinical competence, resulting in a mean score of 4.1, which indicates a high level of agreement. Similarly, report presentations were perceived to enhance understanding of clinical procedures, with 78 respondents (52.0%) strongly agreeing and 52 (34.7%) agreeing (mean = 4.2).

Furthermore, a large proportion of students indicated that long vacation postings improved their confidence, as reflected by 88 respondents (58.7%) who strongly agreed and 44 (29.3%) who agreed (mean = 4.3). Logbook use was also perceived to promote accountability and reflective learning, although with slightly lower mean scores of 3.9 for both accountability and reflection.

The cumulative mean score of 4.07 indicates that students generally agree that logbook documentation and report presentations during long vacation postings contribute positively to the development of clinical competence among student radiographers.

Discussion of Findings

This study examined the impact of long vacation logbooks and report presentations on the clinical competence of student radiographers at the University of Maiduguri. The findings provide valuable insights into student participation, reflective practices, and perceived learning outcomes, while drawing connections with existing literature across similar educational contexts. Accordingly, The study revealed a male-dominated sample (64%), with higher representation among senior students, particularly those in the 500 level (43.3%) and 400 level (36%). Nearly all participants (98.7%) reported attending at least one long vacation clinical posting, confirming that vacation postings are a vital component of radiography education in Maiduguri. Regarding attendance patterns, about two-thirds of the respondents (63.1%) reported always attending the postings, while 28.2% indicated that they attended only sometimes, suggesting a degree of irregular participation possibly resulting from weak enforcement mechanisms. This high participation rate reflects students' recognition of the postings as essential for hands-on learning and skill consolidation. However, the findings revealed significant inconsistency in documentation and reflection practices. Less than half of the respondents (41.3%) kept a logbook during their postings, and among those who did, only 56.5% filled it regularly. Likewise, only 43.3% of students presented formal reports after their clinical experiences. These figures highlight a clear gap between the perceived value of reflective learning and its actual implementation.

The results are consistent with Abdullah Omar et al. (2021), who found that 75.3% of students and 83.3% of teachers in Saudi Arabia believed logbooks improved learning and engagement during clinical rotations. That study also revealed that 67.4% of students credited written feedback for enhancing their performance. In contrast, the low proportion of consistent logbook users in Maiduguri suggests that, while students recognize the educational benefits of such documentation, the absence of structured enforcement and supervision limits its full potential.

The study also found that most students were motivated by the desire for hands-on experience (76.7%), which aligns with the experiential learning theory by Kolb (1984). This reflects that students value practical exposure as the most meaningful form of learning. Similar to O'Connor et al. (2024), who reported that 78% of radiography students in Ireland found clinical logbook documentation instrumental in connecting theory to practice, the Maiduguri findings reinforce the idea that structured clinical experience enhances learning depth. However, barriers such as financial constraints (37.3%), lack of penalties for absence (28%), and poor supervision hindered optimal participation issues also observed by Kumsa et al., (2022) in Ethiopia, where inconsistent supervision limited the effectiveness of logbooks despite students acknowledging their benefits.

Feedback emerged as another critical factor influencing clinical competence. The study showed that 83% of students agreed or strongly agreed that supervisor feedback and report presentations improved their understanding and confidence. This finding mirrors the results of Maduka, et al. (2021), where 88% of Nigerian radiography lecturers agreed that structured logbook assessments enhance competence and documentation accuracy. Unfortunately, in Maiduguri, inconsistent

supervision meant many students filled their logbooks retrospectively or not at all, reducing opportunities for timely feedback and reflection.

Despite these challenges, students' overall perception of long vacation postings was highly positive. Over 90% agreed that they learned better during vacation postings than during regular semester postings, and 84% reported greater confidence in performing clinical tasks after these experiences. These outcomes echo findings by Kipkulei et al. (2022), who noted a 62% improvement in clinical documentation accuracy when logbooks were used systematically. Likewise, Tavares and Boet (2015) found that 65% of educators observed fewer procedural errors when students used logbooks, confirming their effectiveness in skill accuracy and self-evaluation.

In summary, this study reinforces the established understanding that structured logbooks and reflective report presentations are essential tools for building clinical competence, accountability, and professional growth. However, when their use is voluntary or poorly supervised—as in the Maiduguri context—their full educational impact is diminished. The findings call for policy-level reforms to make logbook completion and report presentations mandatory, supported by stronger supervision, structured feedback, and institutional incentives to encourage compliance.

Conclusion

This study concludes that long vacation clinical postings play a vital role in developing the clinical competence of radiography students, while logbook and report presentation has a positive impact on clinical competence of student radiographers at the University of Maiduguri. Students overwhelmingly recognize their value in strengthening practical skills, confidence, and professional readiness. However, inconsistent use of logbooks and report presentations which are crucial for reflective learning are the challenges to their learning effectiveness. The lack of supervision and structured feedback reduces accountability and learning depth.

Recommendations

1. Make logbooks mandatory with clear daily or weekly documentation standards.
2. Integrate report presentations into assessment to promote reflection and communication skills.
3. Strengthen supervision and assign coordinators for logbook review and feedback.
4. Provide financial and logistical support to mitigate travel and accommodation barriers.
5. Establish structured feedback mechanisms between students and supervisors.
6. Introduce digital or mobile-based logbooks for accountability and ease of tracking.
7. Conduct reflective learning workshops for students and supervisors.

REFERENCES

- Abdullah Omer, A. A. (2021). Using logbooks to enhance students' learning: Lessons from a mixed-methods study in an undergraduate surgical rotation. *Sudan Journal of Medical Sciences*, 16(3), 409-429. <https://doi.org/10.18502/sjms.v16i3.9701>
- Akpaniwo, G. M., Sadiq, A. A., Danfulani, M., Abubakar, U., Mohammed, A., Iliyasu, Y. I., & Sheshu, O. P. (2018). Challenges faced by undergraduate radiography students in Sokoto

- Northwest Nigeria, during long vacation clinical posting. *International Journal of Health Sciences and Research*, 8(2), 29-36.
- Awang Besar, M. N., Kamarudin, M. A., & Mohamad Rom, F. Z. (2025). Exploring medical student's experiences with logbook in clinical training: A qualitative study. *Education in Medicine Journal*, 17(3), 43-56. <https://doi.org/10.21315/eimj2025.17.3.4>
- Awang Besar, M. N., Kamarudin, M. A., & Mohamad Rom, F. Z. (2025). Exploring medical student's experiences with logbook in clinical training: A qualitative study. *Education in Medicine Journal*, 17(3), 43-56. <https://doi.org/10.21315/eimj2025.17.3.4>
- Chia, D. M., Magaji, G. O., & Ugande, A. A. (2024). Fundamental advancements in structured reporting in radiology. *International Journal of Research and Scientific Innovation*, XI(IX), 159-177. doi:10.51244/ijrsi.2024.1109017
- Coleman, P., Jimenez, Y., Kumsa, M., Punch, A., Jeyandraban, M., & Akudjedu, T. (2024). Explaining the practicum experiences of diagnostic radiography undergraduates in Australia and Ethiopia using the theory of human relatedness. *Radiography*, 30(2), 517-523. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.radi.2024.01.007>
- Elechi, U. S., Adeoye, A. F., Obiye, S. O., Umar, S. A., Ezeamii, V. C., Iwu, P., Ugwuanyi, K. O., & Abone, K. (2025). Digital transformation in radiography practice in Nigeria: A comprehensive review. *Journal of Medical Science, Biology, and Chemistry*, 2(1), 92-103. <https://doi.org/10.69739/jmsbc.v2i1.562>
- Epstein, R. M. (2002). Defining and assessing professional competence. *JAMA*, 287(2), 226. <https://doi.org/10.1001/JAMA.287.2.226>
- Hmelo-Silver, C. E. (2004). Problem-based learning: What and how do students learn? *Educational Psychology Review*, 16(3), 235-266. <https://doi.org/10.1023/b:edpr.0000034022.16470.f3>
- Idowu, B. M. (2018). Postgraduate radiology education in Nigeria: Looking backward and forward. *South African Journal of Radiology*, 22(1). <https://doi.org/10.4102/sajr.v22i1.1362>
- Kilminster, S., Cottrell, D., Grant, J., & Jolly, B. (2007). AMEE guide No. 27: Effective educational and clinical supervision. *Medical Teacher*, 29(1), 2-19. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01421590701210907>
- Kipkulei, J., Kangethe, S., Boibanda, F., Jepngetich, H., Lotodo, T., & Kirinyet, J. (2022). Assessment methods used during clinical years of undergraduate medical education at Moi University School of Medicine, Kenya. *Health*, 14(03), 296-305. <https://doi.org/10.4236/health.2022.143023>
- Kolb, D.A., (1984). *Experiential learning: Experience as the source of learning and development*. Englewood Cliffs, NJ: Prentice Hall.
- Kumsa, M., Lemu, B., Nguse, T., Omiyi, D., & Akudjedu, T. (2022). Clinical placement challenges associated with radiography education in a low-resource setting: A qualitative exploration of the Ethiopian landscape. *Radiography*, 28(3), 634-640. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.radi.2022.04.014>
- Maduka, B. U., Ugwu, A. C., & Adirika, B. N. (2021). Perception of radiography lecturers towards the proposed doctor of radiography program. *Egyptian Journal of Radiology and Nuclear Medicine*, 52(1). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s43055-021-00488-z>

- Mifflin, Campbell, & Price. (2000). A conceptual framework to guide the development of self-directed, lifelong learning in problem-based medical curricula. *Medical Education*, 34(4), 299-306. <https://doi.org/10.1046/j.1365-2923.2000.00564.x>
- Mokhtar, M. N., Suhaini, S. A., Abdullah, F. H., Teo, R., Izaham, A., & Ismail, N. A. (2024). A survey of anaesthetic training logbook management among postgraduate students. *BMC Medical Education*, 24(1). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12909-024-05859-4>
- O'Connor, M., & McNulty, J. (2024). Radiography students' viewpoints of the clinical learning environment: A cross-sectional study. *Radiography*, 30(1), 367-374. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.radi.2023.12.005>
- Ogbu, S. O. I. (2008). Radiography students' perceptions of clinical placements—A Nigerian perspective. *Radiography*, 14(2), 154-161.
- Ohagwu, C. C., Eze, J. C., Ezugwu, E. E., Umeano, J. K., Ochie, K., Eze, C. U., & Barde, M. (2016). Challenges of training and clinical skill acquisition in radiography education: perceptions of students in resource-poor southeastern Nigeria: peer reviewed original article. *South African Radiographer*, 54(2), 7-13.
- Oxford University Press (1989) *Oxford English Dictionary. 2nd ed.* Oxford: Clarendon Press.
- Saba, M. A., Ghotbi, N., Haghjoo, M., Shamsi, A., & Bagheri, R. (2024). Design, implementation, and evaluation of a logbook for clinical education of undergraduate physiotherapy students. *Journal of Modern Rehabilitation*, 18(2), 189-198. <https://doi.org/10.18502/jmr.v18i2.15976>
- Sandy, P. T., Meyer, J. T., Oduniyi, O. S., & Mavhandu-Mudzusi, A. H. (2021). *Paramedic students' confidence and satisfaction with clinical simulations of an emergency medical care programme in South Africa: A cross-sectional study.* *Health SA Gesondheid*, 26. <https://doi.org/10.4102/hsag.v26i0.1522>
- Shafuda, S., Daniels, E., & Karera, A. (2024). Bridging theory and practice: Experiences of diagnostic radiography students during clinical training in resource-constrained settings. *Journal of Medical Radiation Sciences*, 72(2), 225-233. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jmrs.854>
- Tavares, W., & Boet, S. (2015). On the assessment of paramedic competence: A narrative review with practice implications. *Prehospital and Disaster Medicine*, 31(1), 64-73. <https://doi.org/10.1017/s1049023x15005166>
- Ugwu, A. C., Udo Benjamin, E., Ifenatuora Jennifer, M., & Felix, E. O. (2009). Evidence based medical imaging practice in Nigeria: A paradigm or a placebo? *European Journal of Radiography*, 1(4), 169-172. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejradi.2010.07.001>
- Upadhayay, N., & Guragain, S. (2022). Perception of students and teachers on practice of logbook maintenance and its value in pre-clinical years. *Janaki Medical College Journal of Medical Science*, 10(2), 28-37. <https://doi.org/10.3126/jmcjms.v10i2.47865>